

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INTERNET RESOURCES IN FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

V. Abdieva¹

Abstract:

This article talks about the formation of the intercultural communication competence of the future foreign language teachers through Internet resources, and it is mentioned that the order in which they are used will be appropriate for the purpose.

Key words: technology, communication, dialogue, e-mail, CD, global

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In today's rapidly developing age, science and technology are growing rapidly. Progress is being made in every field. In particular, great changes and significant progress are being made in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communicative and informational tools is required in the course of foreign language lessons. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Teaching Foreign Languages and the Evaluation of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process,

¹ *Abdieva Vazira Ashurovna, Doctoral student of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; — it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; — use of tape recorders and cassettes, which is considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. In the process of globalization, it is difficult to imagine our life without the Internet. It is one of the most effective ways to use it effectively in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. You will have the opportunity to communicate with people who speak a foreign language through the Internet. You can improve writing practice by writing letters via e-mail. Bringing modern communication technologies into the educational process, using them purposefully and correctly, and using them to increase the student's interest in a foreign language and increase the effectiveness of teaching is the most important issue. Through this, the opportunity to use innovative technologies of education will be created and the demand will increase. Today, there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. If they use wide and various methods to cover the topic in classes, the efficiency of the lesson will be high and the increase of students' interest in the lesson will be ensured. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by introducing innovations into the educational process and implementing them. The use of various role-playing and action games in the teaching of foreign language classes increases the interest in the lesson and language learning. It helps students to communicate with others by working in pairs or small groups. The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important ways to illuminate the topic and deliver it to students. It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to cover the same topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is appropriate to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammatical rules related to the topic. It will also be easy to remember if these are presented through graphic organizers. The effectiveness of using different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also high. Using tables in the educational process, students can learn a certain grammatical rule, for example, making sentences using tenses, placing new words. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language is high, effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies in the educational process will make this process effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies lies in their correct and effective use in the educational process.

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